

Dynamically triggering of photoreactions for high performance and efficiency

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Abstract

This opinion article provides the readers with a general insight into photochemical reaction engineering and which parameters need to be considered for the development of sustainable light-driven processes. The demand for comparability of experimental data and the need to couple mass transport and photon balances are discussed, aspects that are often overseen in current research. It will be explained how dynamic tuning of the radiation field with time and space will help to exploit the coupling of mass and photon transport towards improving the efficiency of light-driven transformations. From these evaluations, conclusions on the current research demand will be drawn.

1 Light-driven chemistry

Light-driven chemical reactions have attracted significant attention during recent years as highly-potent alternative to conventional thermal reactions.[1–4] Initiating reactions with light gives access to synthetic routes that are not accessible through electronic ground state chemistry driven by heat.[5,6] Light is a traceless reagent and thus reduces the required downstream purification efforts. The selective activation of chemicals under often mild conditions goes along with an increased sustainability through reduction of waste and energy consumption as well as avoidance of toxic or hazardous chemicals. Photochemical reactions are intrinsically electrified when operated with artificial light sources and thus can be powered by low carbon electricity.[7] Photocatalytic and photosensitized reactions give access to a broad scope of chemical transformations with high tolerance to functional groups, a crucial requirement for the synthesis of active pharmaceutical ingredients.[8,9] Beside chemical synthesis, light-driven chemistry is also highly attractive for air and water remediation as well as for the activation of small molecules.[10] The activation of CO₂ and N₂ are prominent examples that are currently in focus of research.[11] Solar-driven water splitting may provide access to solar hydrogen as one of several

Figure 1: Publications mainly focusing on synthetic photochemistry cited in a recent comprehensive review by Noel et al.[4]

approaches to harvest solar energy.[12,13] The recent advancements in the field can be attributed to three major drivers: progress in efficiency and performance of light-emitting diodes (LEDs),[14,15] photoreactor design and advances in synthetic photochemistry, yielding a leap in knowledge that is reflected in the increasing number of publications during the last 10 years (Figure 1).

Remarkably, numerous publications reported on the application of photochemistry on industrial scale recently.[16–19] At the edge of transferring lab results to application, reaction engineering aspects become increasingly important in addition to chemical aspects. These include the reactor design, the light sources as well as measures to control the reaction progress and beneficially influence the underlying reaction network.

2 The interface between chemistry and chemical engineering

Despite the recent progress in light-driven chemistry, a gap between chemistry and chemical engineering becomes visible, where only few activities try to leverage synergies between the disciplines. In the opinion of the authors, this situation raises an unnecessary hurdle for future advances in light-driven reactions. Instead, chemists and chemical engineers should collaborate synergistically to accelerate research on the fundamental as well as the application level.

Research in photochemistry is driven by the need to access certain chemical motifs through efficient and sustainable synthetic strategies. The development of new syntheses strategies is based on expert knowledge on molecular properties of the reactant and the chemical environment. Consequently, syntheses routes are explored with strong focus on previous experiences, especially with respect to the effect of chemical parameters such as solvent, concentration, etc. to overcome the laborious experimental exploration of a huge parameter space on the way to the required reaction control. This screening eventually leads to identification of optimal reaction conditions within this restricted parameter space. In this context, efficiency is frequently linked to the yield in relation to the reaction time.

In terms of chemical engineering, reaction control can be achieved by chemical means through adjusting the reaction kinetics with chemical parameters like the solvent, co-solvent, protection of functional groups or the sequence of reactions. Complementary to this, reaction control can also be achieved with more technical parameters such as temperature, pressure or mixing. For photoreactions, the photon flux is the key parameter that determines the rate of the photoreaction. Hence, the irradiation field, i.e., the spatial, temporal and spectral distribution of light intensity, represents a further parameter that can be utilized to gain additional reaction control. Similar to the chemistry perspective, the yield of the reaction is a key performance indicator. In addition to that, other performance indicator such as reaction rates, space-time-yield or photonic/electrical efficiency are relevant as these are the link to the reactor design and concept as well as the process economics on industrial scale.

3 Reactor design

The design of the photoreactor is mainly governed by the need to guide photons efficiently to the reaction solution.[20–24] In this context, the properties of the light source and the reactor, including the geometry and the wall materials, must be aligned such that as much photons as possible reach the reaction solution. Furthermore, spatial, temporal and spectral distribution of the intensity are defined by the reactor design. On the laboratory scale, slight variations of the experimental setup might lead to significant deviations within experiments. Consequently, special attention should be paid to well-documented and characterized experimental setups as means to ensure comparability across different experiments and scientific studies (D. Kowalczyk, P. Li, A. Abbas, J. Eichhorn, P. Buday, M. Heiland, A.

Pannwitz, F.Schacher, W.Weigand, C.Streb, D.Ziegenbalg, zenodo doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5614942). On the industrial scale, technical constraints of the light sources might limit design flexibilities for photoreactors. To overcome these, new techniques to ensure an efficient heat removal from the light sources, especially for LEDs, were developed recently. Direct immersion of LEDs into a heat transfer fluid enhances heat transport and thus allows reduction of the size of the light source unit (Figure 2).[25] The use of wirelessly powered light sources presents another concept, that goes beyond the use of conventional immersion light sources.[26]

Figure 2: Industrial scale LED immersion lamp with direct liquid cooling.[25]

Micro- and millistructured reactors, also frequently referenced as flow reactors, provide a high degree of control over the irradiation conditions and can be used to avoid large gradients in radiation intensity by using short optical depth.[27,28] Furthermore, the projection of the reaction time coordinate to the reactor length enables adjustment of light intensity with reaction progress. The small size of such reactors together with the low internal volume made such photoreactors very popular in synthetic laboratories.[29,30] Continuous operation furthermore allows for straightforward automation of the experimental setup and thus high throughput screening experimentation. Photoreactions frequently require long residence times in the photoreactor which are related to low flow velocities and with this a slow mass transport.[31] To overcome this issue, oscillatory flow conditions or ultrasound might be used to provide both an intense mass transport together with long residence time.[32–34]

Scale-up strategies include classical numbering-up of capillary flow reactors as well as dedicated tank reactors with larger volumes. Various reactor designs have been shown to be scalable and were applied on industrial scale.[35–37]

4 Reaction control

The fundamental correlations between apparent reaction rate and incident photon flux are known since decades.[38] For simple photoreactions, the reaction rate is proportional to the absorbed photon flux, given that no additional consecutive reactions, such as e.g., radical chain reactions, are involved. Complex reactions that involve several steps or catalytic cycles, e.g. photoredox reactions, show more complex kinetic correlations that may also involve heat and mass transport. Even though it is commonly known that the rate of light-driven reactions is governed by the photon flux, temporal changes of irradiation have not been exploited as tool until recently, when it was found to be a suited mean to tune the performance of light-driven reactions. Temporal control over the rate of the light-driven step allows also to tune the selectivity and improve the lifetime of chemical systems.

Recent publications report on the beneficial application of periodic or pulsed irradiation for hydrogen evolution, leading to an increase of the apparent reaction rate normalized to the time-averaged photon flux and thus to a higher efficiency of energy conversion.[39,40] Hence, research on the use of imposed dynamic irradiation, i.e. the desired temporal change of the incident photon flux represents a valuable strategy to develop high performance photoreactions.

Dynamic irradiation may be realized by electronic control of the LEDs but goes along with an overall reduction of the time-average photon flux that is available within the photoreactor. Hence, strategies

are required that provide a high overall photon flux to the reactor but still realize dynamic irradiation. Installation of multiple, spatially separated light sources on a continuous photoreactors is one concept. The spatial separation of the light sources creates irradiated and not irradiated regions. Thus, a given control volume flowing through this reactor is first irradiated, then enters a dark region and is subsequently irradiated again. Hence, the active components, i.e. the photocatalyst or photosensitizer, are dynamically irradiated while the light sources are operated continuously without decrease of the incident photon flux.

Figure 3: a) CAD-Drawing of 3D-printed flow photoreactor using 2 spatially separated LEDs. b) CFD-simulation of the same reactor with an installed mixing element. c) Initial reaction rates of the photocatalytic nitrobenzene reduction using different mixing elements (H-P, V-P, wall, double mixer), a single pulsed LED (e.g. irradiation time / dark time, in ms) and 2 LEDs. [41]

For the photocatalyzed reduction of nitrobenzene with TiO_2 as catalyst, the initial reaction rate and with this also the photonic efficiency increased by about 30 % when the reactor is operated with two spatially distributed light sources (Figure 3).[41] Considering the fast absorption of light in TiO_2 suspensions, movement of catalyst particles to and away from the light source also leads to changing irradiation conditions for the particle. Consequently, provoked movement of the TiO_2 particles along the irradiation trajectory was exploited by manipulating the hydrodynamics, i.e. mass transport, in the irradiation zones by installation of different static mixers. This approach led to an increase of the initial reaction rate by about 12 %. Pulsation of the LED caused a decrease of the initial reaction rate as a result of the reduced time-averaged availability of photons. Analyzes of the photonic efficiency, that considers the time averaged photon flux, showed that the pulsed operation leads to an increase of the photonic efficiency by a factor of 4 especially for very short irradiation periods, emphasizing the potential of dynamic irradiation and possibilities of technical implementation.

Homogeneous systems can benefit from dynamic irradiation as well. Reducing the temporal availability of photons through appropriate reactor design and enhanced mass transport along the light ray trajectory led to an improvement of the turnover number of the light-driven water oxidation catalysis by a factor of 11 (M. Sender, F. Huber, M. Moersch, D. Kowalczyk, J. Hniopek, S. Klingler, M. Schmitt, S. Kaufhold, K. Siewerth, J. Popp, B. Mizaikoff, D. Ziegenbalg, S. Rau, chemrxiv doi: 10.33774/chemrxiv-2021-wnqd3-v3). This is associated with a 31-fold increase of the photonic efficiency. The decreased availability of photons reduces the probability of the detrimental oxidation of the photosensitizer.

For the copper-photocatalyzed C-F functionalization, it was found that pulsed LED irradiation not only changes the reaction rate but also the selectivity of the reaction.[42] Even for light-initiated radical reactions, such as photochlorinations, a positive effect of dynamic irradiation was found. While the apparent reaction rate was independent of the pulsed irradiation, the selectivity towards side-chain chlorinations increased even under strongly intensified conditions.[43]

Exploitation of the irradiation field to control photoreactions requires a thorough understanding of the radiation field. This can be gained by photonic characterization of photochemistry equipment and includes chemical actinometry, radiometry and numerical simulations like ray tracing or modelling of the radiative transfer equation.[44,45] Even though various techniques are at hand to measure photons or calculate their spatial and temporal distribution, photonic characterization is seldom reported in the literature. Chemical actinometry measures the photon flux incident inside the reactor in an integral manner. Complementary, radiometry can measure photon fluxes also as a function of time. Numerical methods do not have practical restrictions but always require experimental validation. The demand for reliable actinometers that can be applied for various spectral ranges, most importantly for the UVA and visible region, has recently triggered research on new chemical actinometer systems as well as on reliable measurement procedures.[46] Radiometric methods were proposed as complementary methods that can also provide spatial insights into the radiation field.[47]

3 Research demands

Contrary to former times, the increasing research activities in light-driven reactions are picked-up by chemical industries now. With this, suited strategies are required for transferring light-driven reactions from lab to industry but the required knowledge is still in its infancy. Today, the importance of the interface between chemistry and chemical engineering becomes clearly visible and unravels the demand for interdisciplinary research, that is by no means a one-way road to application. Reaction control strategies such as dynamic irradiation may yield valuable insights into limiting parameters that can be overcome by tuning either molecular parameters, e.g. photocatalyst, light absorber or other chemically active components, or technical parameters, e.g. reactor design, operation conditions or a different light source.[48]

The authors envision that a strong focus on comparability of experimental results, including the free and easy access of research data following the FAIR principles together with comprehensive characterization, sensitivity studies and documentation will accelerate research on light-driven reactions, and is a necessary step towards Big Data analysis (D. Ziegenbalg, A. Pannwitz, S. Rau, B. Dietzek-Ivanšić, C. Streb, zenodo doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5575037).[49] In this context, knowledge of the spectral photon flux absorbed by active components is of utmost importance to correlate experimental results in a comprehensive evaluation (D. Kowalczyk, P. Li, A. Abbas, J. Eichhorn, P. Buday, M. Heiland, A. Pannwitz, F. Schacher, W. Weigand, C. Streb, D. Ziegenbalg, (2021). zenodo doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5614942.). Broad implementation of high-throughput techniques may further accelerate progress in light-driven chemistry.[50]

To date, the potential of dynamic irradiation is virtually unexplored. Considering the significant improvements and major alterations induced by temporal changes of the irradiation conditions illustrated in the examples above, in-depth understanding of the associated processes will open the avenue to highly efficient and sustainable chemical processes. We believe that exploitation of this promising concept requires joint efforts at the interface between chemistry and chemical engineering.

Prerequisites for the technical implementation of dynamic irradiation are light sources that enable the required temporal changes together with suited reactor concepts. Furthermore, advanced reactor concepts satisfying the demand of mass transport in homogeneous as well as heterogeneous phase are required that seamlessly integrate with the light sources to ensure high photonic and electric efficiency of the reactors.

Consequently, reaction engineering is not only an essential tool for transferring chemical reactions to application, but also a valuable addition to fundamental research to elucidate mechanistic contexts as well as to guide molecular developments towards application.

Conflict of interest statement

Dirk Ziegenbalg has patent #WO2020228980 issued to Alexander Peschl and Dirk Ziegenbalg.

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